

THE INTERNATIONAL MONETARY FUND AS A POLITICAL TOOL: A STUDY OF THE IMPACT OF THE FUND'S PROGRAMS ON IRAQ'S ECONOMIC SOVEREIGNTY (2011–2020)

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Abstract

This study seeks to investigate the complex and intertwined relationship between the International Monetary Fund (IMF) and its programs' impact on Iraq's economic sovereignty during a critical decade (2011–2020). The Fund is not viewed merely as a lender or technical advisor but as a politically influential actor capable of shaping the economic policies of borrowing states. This raises fundamental questions about these states'—such as Iraq's—ability to chart their own independent development path. The study concludes, among other findings, that the conditions imposed by IMF programs (such as deficit reduction, freezing public employment, and cutting expenditures) significantly constrained the fiscal space available to the Iraqi government. These constraints, despite their apparent economic rationale, affected the government's ability to allocate resources in line with its independent developmental and social priorities, representing a setback to a significant aspect of financial sovereignty. One of the main recommendations is that Iraq should heavily invest in building the capacities of its national cadres specialized in economics, law, and international finance. This would enable Iraq to negotiate the terms of IMF programs from a position of strength, better understand the available options, and identify conditions most compatible with its national development goals without compromising its sovereignty.

Keywords: International Monetary Fund, Iraqi Economy, Economic Sovereignty.

INTRODUCTION

The Iraqi economy has suffered greatly over past decades due to wars, sanctions, and the deterioration of the security situation in the aftermath of 2003, and it continues to endure significant hardship to this day. The situation further worsened after 2011, following the Arab Spring and the emergence of extremist organizations that controlled large parts of Iraqi territory.

This period, particularly after 2011, was characterized by a loss of economic planning, weak strategies and policies in managing economic affairs and its various sectors, and complete and direct dependence on oil as the main source of income and as the primary resource for the state's general budget. This led to a weakened contribution of non-oil sectors to the GDP. Exacerbating this suffering were mismanagement of public funds, administrative and financial corruption, the marginalization and exclusion of experienced and competent economic cadres from managing economic institutions, as well as instability in oil prices—which dropped sharply in mid-2014—and the ongoing political and security instability and the war on terrorism. These factors led Iraq into its current economic and financial crisis, which is considered one of the most severe in the modern history of the Iraqi economy. All these conditions forced Iraq, like other developing countries, to seek solutions to address the crisis,

resorting to borrowing from international financial institutions, foremost among them the IMF, as one of these solutions. However, there was excessive reliance on borrowing from these institutions. Consequently, Iraq's inability to meet the burdens of these loans, coupled with their massive size, trapped Iraq in a dilemma of external debt, deepened its economic dependency, and tied Iraq to the mechanisms of the capitalist economy through the prominent role played by the World Bank in imposing programs and shaping fiscal and economic policy in Iraq.

Iraq was among the countries that excessively resorted to external borrowing and still suffers from the consequences of these debts, in addition to the ongoing economic and social challenges, especially after submitting to the conditions of the World Bank. These loans became an economic burden because Iraq could not repay them within the specified period, and the debt service grew to exceed the principal debt itself. This forced Iraq to comply with the conditions, regulations, and programs imposed by the World Bank on Iraq from 2011 to 2020.

Through this study, the role of the IMF in intervening in Iraq's internal affairs and the impact of this intervention on Iraq's economic and political aspects will be demonstrated.

Research Problem and Questions

The core problem of this study lies in the inherent tension between Iraq's need for financial and technical support from the IMF and the potential constraints and influences that come with the conditions attached to such support, which may affect Iraq's ability to make independent economic decisions serving its developmental objectives and economic sovereignty. Does the IMF exercise influence beyond its technical role to become a force shaping internal policies? And what is the true price Iraq pays—if any—for such support?

Accordingly, the study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- What is the nature of the IMF programs implemented in Iraq after 2003, and what are their main conditions?
- How did these conditions affect the formulation of fiscal and monetary policies in Iraq?
- To what extent did the IMF programs restrict Iraq's ability to make independent economic decisions regarding its vital sectors (such as oil, industry, and services)?

Importance of the Study

The importance of this study lies in shedding light on the true nature of IMF policies in both their political and economic dimensions, revealing the underlying implications of the development slogan and economic adjustment projects, placing them within their proper theoretical context, and clarifying their impact in obstructing political development and achieving an acceptable level of economic welfare in the Third World, particularly Iraq. The study's significance also lies in highlighting the role played by global economic institutions (the IMF) in influencing developing countries—particularly Iraq—and revealing some figures about the growth and deficit levels Iraq has reached under the IMF's borrowing and financing policies.

Study Hypotheses

This study is based on the following hypotheses:

- There is a negative impact of the IMF's intervention in Iraq's internal affairs on the Iraqi economy.
- The IMF plays a role in shaping economic and political policies in Iraq after 2011.
- IMF policies and programs have had an effect on Iraq's internal affairs.

METHODOLOGY

In order to achieve the aim of this study, the researcher will follow the **descriptive and analytical approach**, describing and analyzing the policies and programs implemented by the IMF in Iraq, then analyzing their impact on various aspects of economic sovereignty.

Additionally, the **critical approach**, which predominates in this study, will be used to critique the theory of IMF intervention in internal affairs through lending and the conditions it imposes on borrowing states. Particular focus will be placed on the negative aspects arising from the IMF's political and economic interventions in Iraq during the study period.

First Section: Stages of Iraq's Engagement with the IMF

Iraq's involvement in IMF financial and technical assistance programs provided it with an opportunity to avoid the acute part of the ongoing crisis, offered an international oversight umbrella over the Iraqi government's performance, and increased the governance of public institutions, correcting the deviation that infiltrated state institutions due to nepotism, corruption, and the domination of political parties over economic decision-making in alignment with their political agendas at the expense of development and stability (Kazzar, 2021).

The experience of past years has revealed that the consensual model of governance in Iraq has been characterized by the absence of an economic vision and weak policies necessary for economic reform and the development of agricultural, industrial, and service sectors, as well as waste of resources and deepening of structural imbalances through continued reliance on oil revenues to finance the budget and economy and absorb unemployment, without recognizing the risks of tying the economic and financial fate of the country to a resource dependent on external factors (Al-Zubaidi & Al-Talqani, 2016).

Accordingly, international institutions can help design a new economic framework suitable for Iraq's reality, limiting the misuse of oil revenues by political party mafias, away from development and stability. The public financial reform program also provides hope for correcting budgetary plans and programs in a way that serves economic balance by stimulating various economic sectors, supporting low-income groups, and activating alternative financial channels to oil by reforming the tax system and activating the financial market to absorb public surpluses and channel them into investment rather than the staggering consumption Iraq currently witnesses (Al-Maamouri & Al-Tu'mah, 2018).

This section reviews the stages of Iraq's cooperation with the IMF, as follows:

Subsection 1: First and Second Stand-By Arrangements (2003–2008 and 2008–2013)

Iraq has been a founding member of the World Bank and IMF since 1944, participating alongside developing countries in establishing the Fund. Iraq had several dealings with the IMF and World Bank, receiving loans between 1950–1973 for agriculture, education, flood control, wireless communications, and transportation. The last loan was received in 1979 (Kazzar, 2021).

However, the relationship deteriorated when the former Iraqi regime decided to stop providing the IMF with economic data, and it was not restored until after 2003. The relationship was governed by UN Security Council Resolution 1483 of 2003, which obliged Iraq to cooperate positively with the IMF and World Bank to settle Iraq's external debts through the Paris Club agreement. This resolution was binding on Iraq, not optional, based on the view that Iraq's stability was part of regional and global economic stability, particularly since Iraq was then under Chapter VII of the UN Charter, weakening its sovereignty and its relations with international parties (Al-Maamouri & Al-Tu'mah, 2018).

The Iraqi economic reform program supported by the Stand-By Arrangement aimed to address urgent balance-of-payments needs, align spending with lower global oil prices, and ensure debt sustainability. The program also included measures to protect the poor, strengthen public financial management, support financial sector stability, and curb corruption. Iraq required international support to implement these policies (Al-Zubaidi & Al-Talqani, 2016).

Thus, cooperation resumed through the 2003 Madrid Donors' Conference to raise reconstruction funds, and particularly through settling debts with the Paris Club after the IMF determined that Iraq's debt capacity was very weak (unable to service even 0% of its debt), prompting the IMF to recommend writing off 90% of Iraq's debt. Iraq then signed the first Stand-By Arrangement, which included conditions such as adjusting fiscal policy and raising fuel prices to curb smuggling to neighboring countries (Hasheesh & Shahab, 2025).

After signing the first SBA in 2005, Iraq secured the second tranche of debt forgiveness (30%), bringing the total debt forgiven to 60%. The agreement concluded successfully in 2008, after which another 20% was written off, totaling about \$100 billion in external debt and rescheduling the remaining debt until 2028, with all interest payments halted since 2005—achieving significant benefits for Iraq (Zhzar, 2018).

The relationship remained positive through the second SBA in 2008, particularly concerning debt management, until its term ended in 2013.

Subsection 2: Third Stand-By Arrangement of 2015

In 2015, Iraq experienced a major fiscal deficit, expected to persist for years despite efforts to stabilize the situation. Obtaining new loans to finance the deficit implied a sharp rise in public debt, projected to peak at 85% of GDP in 2018 before declining to 75% by 2021, provided recommended fiscal adjustments were implemented (Al-Fadhil, 2024).

At the end of 2015, Iraq entered negotiations for a third SBA. On July 7, 2016, the IMF Executive Board approved a \$5.34 billion SBA to support Iraq's economic reform program, enabling the immediate disbursement of approximately \$1.24 billion (IMF press release on www.imf.org).

Under this SBA, Iraq committed to key structural benchmarks, requiring a series of measures and reforms (Al-Fadhli, 2021). At the fiscal level, the government undertook significant financial correction, mainly through cuts in inefficient capital spending while protecting social spending. The revised 2016 fiscal program and 2017 draft budget were consistent with the SBA. Further gradual fiscal improvements were envisaged through increased non-oil revenues, reduced current expenditures, and reforms to the electricity sector, subsidies, and state-owned enterprises to create fiscal space for more effective investment supporting economic growth.

Financial sector stability measures included strengthening the Central Bank's legal framework, restructuring state-owned banks, maintaining the current exchange rate to ensure economic stability, and combating money laundering, terrorism financing, and corruption. Although government performance under the SBA was mixed, corrective actions were agreed upon to keep the program on track. Strong implementation and international support remained crucial (Kazzar, 2018).

In exchange for these commitments, the IMF provided the \$5.34 billion loan at just 1% interest. Yet, despite these agreements and the significant financial support received from the IMF, Iraq still faces an extremely challenging period in its history, with its economy under intense pressure—even as the Iraqi authorities continued implementing reforms under IMF oversight (Ornez, 2016).

Chapter Two: The Political Implications of IMF Policies on Iraq

The policies and conditions imposed by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) on Iraq in exchange for financial assistance have not only had negative repercussions on the economic sphere but have also adversely affected the political domain. Given the critical role of economic factors in shaping the foreign policy of any state, this chapter examines the IMF's policies as a tool of economic intervention in Iraq and provides an evaluative perspective on Iraq's experience with the IMF. This analysis proceeds as follows:

Section One: IMF Policies as a Tool of Economic Intervention in Iraq

The theory of "soft power" advocates combining both hard and soft power, and economic international intervention is one of the most common and prominent forms of soft power. Major powers often resort to economic means to secure specific gains, underscoring the significance of the economy as a fundamental pillar of state power today and its capacity to enable a state to play a larger role on the international stage through the application of economic pressure (Abd, 2018).

These major powers exert considerable effort to preserve the economic gains they have achieved, as these underpin their effectiveness and ability to fulfill national objectives internationally. To that end, they may even spend vast sums to fuel conflicts or even wars;

however, such measures are costly and unreliable. Consequently, alternative, less costly methods were developed—mechanisms that outwardly aim to regulate international economic relations and support cooperation, yet in reality serve as tools of economic intervention.

As part of their attempt to structure international economic relations in a manner that safeguards their interests, the major powers established new economic rules toward the end of World War II, in favor of the Allies. These rules centered on free trade and international cooperation, operationalized through agreements governing economic relations or establishing monetary, financial, and trade organizations (Arafa, 2022).

Major powers control decision-making within the IMF and use it to pursue their economic interests. “Since its inception, the IMF has imposed onerous conditions that undermine the sovereignty of borrowing states by dictating specific domestic economic policies, effectively placing those states under its tutelage” (Dollar Money, 2021).

The IMF compels borrowing states to embrace a capitalist, market-based economic model, severely affecting their sovereignty. “The Fund closely monitors imports and exports in developing countries, dictates their agricultural programs, and even prescribes their essential goods needs” (Ben Youssef, 2023).

Under deteriorating economic conditions—such as Iraq’s—these states have no choice but to accept such humiliating and sovereignty-compromising conditions in hopes that IMF assistance might revive their economies. “These conditions include currency devaluation, wage reductions, dismantling trade barriers, liberalizing capital flows, raising taxes on goods and services, privatization, and adopting policies aimed at transitioning to a market economy” (Charbel Baer, 1997).

However, these conditional aid packages have largely failed to achieve their purported objectives, and in many cases exacerbated debt crises. “In practice, these conditions did not improve local economic performance; rather, they inflicted serious harm. Devaluations failed to improve trade balances, as indebted states continued to import more than they exported, fueling domestic inflation via imported global inflation” (Ben Youssef, 2022).

Thus, the IMF has functioned as a pliant tool in the hands of major powers to exert economic intervention on borrowing states—contradicting principles won by the Global South, enshrined in United Nations resolutions affirming the right of states to manage their own economies and choose their development paths. Notably, Resolution 803 (1960) declared “permanent sovereignty over natural wealth and resources,” affirming that such resources are inalienable and must remain under national control (UN General Assembly Resolutions 1960/1977).

Similarly, Resolution 3281 (1974), titled The Charter of Economic Rights and Duties of States, asserted in Article 1 that: “Every state has the inalienable right to freely choose its economic, political, social, and cultural systems in accordance with the will of its people, without external interference, coercion, or threat” (Younis, 1991). Article 2 granted states the right to regulate and control foreign investments within their territory according to national laws and priorities, without being compelled to grant preferential treatment.

These resolutions broadened the concept of sovereignty to include economic equality alongside political equality. Nevertheless, major powers have continued to use the IMF to advance their economic agendas, often applying double standards—imposing harsh conditions on developing countries while sparing Eastern European states that embraced capitalism after the Cold War. “In 1976, despite a UN General Assembly demand to cease lending to apartheid South Africa, the IMF, at the behest of the US and UK, extended to South Africa loans exceeding those granted to the entire sub-Saharan Africa” (Chomsky et al., 2001).

Developing countries, including Iraq, have little choice but to accept these conditions, negotiating from a position of weakness. “Although the IMF claims to support democratic institutions in recipient states, in practice it undermines democracy by imposing economic policies. Formally, the IMF imposes nothing, but in reality, the balance of power in negotiations is heavily one-sided” (Benjamin Barber, 2005).

Instead of assisting countries in overcoming economic crises, the IMF has often depleted their resources (Ben Youssef, 2021), leaving behind severe economic consequences. Notably, the 1997 crises in Taiwan, Indonesia, South Korea, and Thailand, as well as Argentina’s collapse in 2001 following massive privatizations and market liberalization, resulted in hunger, panic, 18% unemployment, institutional collapse, and sovereign default (Dhab’, 2008).

Such outcomes heightened public unrest, culminating in the overthrow of Argentina’s President De la Rúa. Clearly, the IMF’s policy of conditionality and selectivity has forced developing nations, including Iraq, into economic liberalization with dire consequences: rising debt burdens, worsening crises, loss of control over domestic projects, suspension of social services, and growing poverty, unemployment, and political instability. These states became easy prey for the IMF, major powers, and multinational corporations, compelled to align their economies with Western interests.

Section Two: Evaluating Iraq’s Experience with the IMF

Iraq’s current financial crisis is the product of multiple economic, political, and security factors. While falling oil prices were the immediate trigger, deeper structural imbalances, low private sector participation, weak performance of non-oil sectors, war expenditures, political instability, corruption, poor public financial management, and sectarian patronage all contributed (Aboud, 2018).

Resorting to IMF loans has not provided an effective solution despite the corrective policies and programs imposed. Consequently, Iraq’s experience with the IMF has both supporters and opponents. This section examines how economic factors influenced Iraq’s foreign relations and the political divisions over its engagement with the IMF.

Subsection One: The Impact of Iraq’s Economic Situation on Foreign Policy

As previously noted, Iraq’s heavy indebtedness, stringent conditions imposed by lenders and international institutions, and deteriorating economy have negatively affected its foreign policy and relations within the Arab world.

Economic factors play a central role in shaping political decisions, particularly foreign policy. Strong economic resources enhance political and military capacity, enable participation in costly arms races and trade, and help maintain a favorable balance of payments (Ismail, 2010).

Adequate resources afford policymakers flexibility and freedom in international relations, while resource-poor states cannot act independently. States reliant on foreign assistance often lose decision-making autonomy due to external pressures (Gabriel Almond, 1998).

Economy and politics are intertwined: politics is about managing societal development in line with individual and collective needs, while the economy meets material requirements. Thus, “politics is the art of the possible” (Robert Dahl, 2010).

Although Iraq is an oil-rich state, reports indicate high unemployment, housing and food crises, declining living standards, widespread poverty, and poor education. Such conditions constrain foreign policy, compelling Iraq to adopt strategies imposed by creditor states (Ontrauzler, 2016).

Iraq’s conflicts over oil have long strained relations with neighbors, notably during the Gulf War. From the late 1970s, Iraq accused Gulf states—particularly Saudi Arabia—of overproducing oil, depressing prices, and damaging Iraq’s economy. This tension escalated, culminating in the 1990 invasion of Kuwait (Marhoon, 1995).

Since then, Iraq-Gulf relations have fluctuated. Following the 1996 Oil-for-Food agreement, relations improved slightly but worsened again after 2003 due to the US-led invasion and subsequent instability. Gulf investment resumed tentatively post-2003 but faltered again after the Arab Spring and the rise of ISIS in 2014 (Jalloud, 2019).

Clearly, Iraq’s economic challenges have shaped its foreign policy, forcing it to prioritize attracting investment and economic cooperation with Gulf and neighboring states.

Subsection Two: Supporters of Iraq’s Engagement with the IMF

Proponents argue that the government’s initial austerity measures were ineffective, given Iraq’s dependence on oil. IMF loans provided short-term liquidity to cover budget deficits and alleviate immediate crises, conditional on reforms. While misuse of funds and corruption posed risks, the IMF loan offered several benefits:

1. Mitigating the fiscal crisis by providing liquidity to cover a \$50 billion deficit (Tamuz Social Development Organization, 2017).
2. Taxing high-income officials to enhance revenue and social equity (Hassan & Al-Rifai, 2020).
3. If invested productively, the loan could increase capital formation, investment, employment, and national income.
4. The low interest rate (1.5%) reduced the debt burden and improved Iraq’s international credit rating.
5. IMF oversight ensured better fiscal discipline and reduced corruption.

6. The loan compelled Iraq to reform its rentier economy and develop non-oil sectors (Al-Nawab, 2021).
7. Requiring international monitoring of spending helped prevent misuse of funds (Al-Obaidi, 2016).

Subsection Three: Opponents of Iraq's Engagement with the IMF

Opponents contend that borrowing was the easiest but most perilous choice, driven by short-term consumption rather than productive investment. Corruption and lack of vision risked creating a debt trap (Al-Nawab, 2021).

They argue for a comprehensive, strategic domestic reform program addressing production diversification, banking reform, private sector development, investment climate improvement, education, and political reform—without reliance on IMF loans.

Critiques include:

1. Poor loan management could trigger another debt crisis, as in Greece (Al-Nawab, 2021).
2. Iraq's regressive tax system shifts the debt burden onto low-income groups (Jabouri, 2017).
3. Reduced public spending harms living standards, increases poverty and crime.
4. Halting public hiring worsens unemployment and fosters informal economies.
5. Taxes on consumers and producers harm savings, investment, and domestic industries, while debt service in foreign currency weakens the dinar and balance of payments.
6. The loan funded recurrent, non-productive expenditures, creating a vicious debt cycle.
7. Debt repayment depends entirely on volatile oil revenues.

In sum, while borrowing may address short-term needs, it is not optimal in the long run unless accompanied by structural reforms, expenditure control, and economic diversification.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study revealed that Iraq, facing acute structural challenges—including overdependence on oil, price volatility, and the repercussions of internal and regional conflicts—found itself compelled to seek financial and technical support from the IMF.

While the Fund provided a critical lifeline during times of crisis, its programs and conditions were not entirely neutral; rather, they reflected a particular economic philosophy and carried implications for Iraq's ability to make independent economic decisions, thereby affecting various dimensions of its economic sovereignty.

The analysis confirmed that while financial support was necessary in the short term, it came with constraints that reshaped spending priorities, restructured key sectors, and ultimately influenced Iraq's sovereign choices in charting its economic future.

Based on the findings, the study arrived at a set of key results and recommendations as follows:

First: Findings

1. The study found that IMF program conditions—such as deficit reduction, freezing public-sector hiring, and cutting expenditures—significantly constrained the Iraqi government’s fiscal space. Although these measures may appear economically rational, they undermined the government’s ability to allocate resources according to its independent developmental and social priorities, representing a setback to an important aspect of fiscal sovereignty.
2. The findings also showed that the recommendations to liberalize markets, privatize certain sectors, and reduce government subsidies, while part of the IMF’s reform agenda, directly impacted Iraq’s ability to steer its critical sectors—including oil, industry, and agriculture—which were seen as potential avenues for diversifying the economy. This influence extended beyond regulatory aspects to the core of the state’s strategic decision-making in managing its resources.
3. Certain IMF program conditions—particularly those related to reducing government subsidies and reforming the wage system—had uneven social and economic repercussions on Iraq’s vulnerable segments. While these outcomes were not intentional per se, they underscore that economic policies are not socially neutral, and their application in fragile contexts requires greater sensitivity to social dynamics.

Second: Recommendations

1. Iraq should make substantial investments in building the capacity of its national cadres specialized in economics, law, and international finance. This would enable Iraq to negotiate IMF program conditions from a position of strength, gain a deeper understanding of available options, and identify terms that are better aligned with its national development goals without compromising sovereignty.
2. Iraq needs to accelerate its efforts to diversify its revenue sources beyond oil. This entails developing non-oil sectors—such as agriculture, industry, tourism, and services—improving the investment climate for both domestic and foreign investors, and strengthening tax and customs revenues. The less Iraq depends on external borrowing, the greater its sovereign space in economic decision-making.
3. Instead of waiting for IMF-imposed conditions, Iraq should adopt a comprehensive, internally-driven structural reform agenda. These reforms should aim to strengthen good governance, combat corruption, improve public spending efficiency, and build strong, transparent economic institutions. Internal reform reduces Iraq’s reliance on the IMF and thus diminishes external pressures.

References

- 1) Ornez Ozlu, *Development and Reconstruction of the Iraqi Economy*, trans. Iraq Research Center, 1st ed., Baghdad: Al-Hawra Trading, Printing, and Publishing Co., 2016.
- 2) Ontrauzler, *Development and Reconstruction of the Iraqi Economy*, trans. Iraq Research Center, Baghdad: Al-Hawra Trading, Printing, and Publishing Co., 2016.
- 3) Iyad Hamad Abd, "The External Debt Crisis of Developing Countries: Its Causes and Remedies," *Journal of Anbar University for Economic and Administrative Sciences*, No. 2, Baghdad, 2018.
- 4) Ihab Ali Al-Nawab, "Implications of the New Loan on Iraq's Conditions," *Al-Naba'a Information Network*, 2016, available at: www.annabaa.org (accessed 20/9/2021).
- 5) Benjamin Barber, *Fear's Empire*, trans. Omar Al-Ayoubi, Dar Al-Kitab Al-Arabi, Beirut, Lebanon, 2005.
- 6) Gabriel A. Almond, *Comparative Politics Today: A World View*, trans. Hisham Abdallah, 1st ed., Amman: Al-Ahlia Publishing & Distribution, 1998.
- 7) Hamed Hassan Al-Jubouri, "Causes and Potential Implications of the IMF Loan to Iraq," *Journal of Legal and Political Sciences*, Al-Mustansiriya University, Vol. 3, No. 4, 2017.
- 8) Hassan Latif Al-Zubaidi & Sarah Al-Talqani, "Economic Transformation in Iraq: Problems and Alternatives," *Kufa Journal of Law, University of Kufa, College of Administration and Economics*, Vol. 22, No. 3, 2016.
- 9) Haidar Wahab Aboud, "A Study on the Legal and Political Nature of Public Loans," *Journal of Al-Turath University College*, No. 8, Baghdad, Iraq, 2018.
- 10) Khamees Mohammed Hassan & Iftikhar Mohammed Manahi Al-Rifa'i, "IMF Loans to Developing Countries: Economic Aid or a Mechanism of Intervention and Economic Domination," *Journal of Al-Ma'moun University College, Iraq*, No. 8, 2020.
- 11) Dollar Money, Seegene et al., *The Beautiful and the Ugly American Economy: The American Empire*, Vol. 1, Al-Shorouk Library, 1st ed., Cairo, 2021.
- 12) Robert Dahl, *Democracy and Its Critics*, trans. Namir Abbas Mudhaffar, Arab Institute for Studies, Beirut, 2010.
- 13) Zaid Abdul-Jaleel Marhoon, *Gulf-Iraqi Relations: The Geopolitical Weight Structure*, Center for Strategic Studies, No. 47, 1995.
- 14) Saeed Ali Muhammed Al-Obaidi, *Public Finance Economics*, Dar Dijla, Amman, 2016.
- 15) Samihah Al-Dab', *Multinational Corporations and International Law*, Master's Thesis, Faculty of Law, Public Law Department, University of Al-Fateh, 2007–2008 academic year.
- 16) Charbel Baer, *External Loans, IMF, and the Third World*, trans. Pierre Akl, Dar Al-Taliaa, Beirut, 1997.
- 17) Saleh Abdulsalam Arafa, *International Organization*, Dar Al-Nahda Al-Arabiya, Cairo, 2022.
- 18) Adel Ahmad Hashish & Magdy Shehab, *International Economic Relations*, New University House, Alexandria, 2025.
- 19) Amer Omran Al-Maamouri & Haidar Hassan Al-Tu'ma, "Economic Transformation in Iraq: Justifications and Stances," *Journal of Administration and Economics, University of Karbala*, Vol. 3, No. 10, 2018.
- 20) Fadhel Karee'a Kazaar, "The IMF and Its Impact on the Iraqi Economy," *Iraqi Journal of Economic Sciences*, Year 19, No. 29, 2021.

- 21) Mohammed Sadiq Ismail, *The Gulf Cooperation Council in the Balance*, Dar Al-Uloom Publishing & Distribution, 1st ed., 2010.
- 22) Mohammed Youssef Mohammed Ali Al-Fadhil, *An Analysis of IMF and World Bank Programs*, Master's Thesis, University of Anbar, 2024.
- 23) Mansour Milad Younis, *Introduction to the Study of International Relations*, Nasser University, 1991.
- 24) Mithaq Khairallah Jalloud, *Iraqi–Gulf Relations*, Strategic Analysis Bulletin, Regional Studies Center – University of Mosul, No. 44, June 2019.
- 25) Nadia Ben Youssef, “The External Debt Crisis in African Countries,” *Dirasat Journal*, published by the Green Book Research and Studies Center, Year 4, No. 12, 2023.
- 26) Noam Chomsky et al., *The United States and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights: The American Empire*, Dar Al-Yazouri, Baghdad, 2001.